

**EFFECTS OF VIRTUAL LABORATORY INSTRUCTIONAL
STRATEGY ON STUDENT'S LEARNING ACHIEVEMENTS IN PHYSICS
IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the issue of organizing virtual laboratory workshops on physics. This approach made it possible to implement part of the educational process in a remote or front-line mode, reduce the costs of implementing laboratory workshops, reduce the risks of expensive equipment being damaged due to unskilled use, and implement new forms of work that are difficult to implement within a traditional laboratory. A clear and deep understanding of the basic laws of physics and its methods is impossible without working in a physics laboratory, as well as without performing home laboratory work. By conducting laboratory research, students not only confirm the known laws of physics, but also learn to work with physical instruments and master the skills of practical research. It was shown that an educational environment aimed at ensuring the development of the student's skills to independently form new knowledge, formulate ideas, concepts, hypotheses about objects and phenomena, including previously unknown ones, recognize the deficits of their own knowledge and competencies, and plan their development.

Keywords: organization of laboratory workshops, virtual instruments, laboratory workshop, models of measuring instruments, virtual laboratory stands

1. Introduction

Physics as a science studies the most general properties and patterns of behavior of material objects and their systems. The fundamental principles of physical science, as well as its most important technical applications, constitute the content

of physics as an educational subject. Methods for presenting the content of a physics course are varied. The leading ones include physical experiment. This is a complex method, which is a system of various teaching actions of the teacher, as well as various techniques for their implementation. This method has variations. An educational physics experiment can be virtual or laboratory. In the first case, it acts as a means of implementing visual teaching methods, in the second as a method of organizing schoolchildren's educational activities aimed at mastering the experience of independent study of physical phenomena. Used in combination with other teaching methods, the educational experiment appears not only in its natural implementation. The development of a system of teaching aids has led to the use of virtual educational environment resources in teaching. A new type of educational visualization has appeared - a virtual educational experiment. However, not everyone accepted it as a necessary and useful learning tool.

2. The problem of using virtual models in training

The virtual experiment, based on high-quality physical and mathematical models of natural phenomena, as a new means of clarity, should not have raised serious objections. On the one hand, animation effects in physics videos have been successfully used before; on the other hand, the use of material or materialized models of real objects has always been considered a very appropriate teaching method, since it ensures a deeper assimilation of educational material [1].

From the above it follows that the virtual experiment as a new teaching tool is worthy of serious attention from both developers and teachers. As part of other teaching aids, it should, it seems, ensure an unconditional increase in the effectiveness of schoolchildren's educational work. There is practically no doubt that field experience, a virtual model of a phenomenon, and an educational text, all of this together should determine a fundamentally new quality of presentation of educational material. However, along with an understanding of the potential usefulness of a virtual experiment, there is concern about the possibility of its excessive and not entirely adequate use in teaching physics. This is not the first time that the problem of the place and role of a virtual experiment in the educational

process in physics has been discussed in methodological science. In a number of cases, it becomes not only the subject of heated discussions, but also irreconcilable polemics.

3. The meaning and role of virtual experiments.

Virtual experiments constitute a large and very important part of the school physics experiment. They have specific didactic tasks and methods of implementation, therefore they are the subject of special consideration in the methodology of teaching physics. Virtual is the teacher's showing of physical phenomena and the connections between them; it is intended to be consumed simultaneously by students throughout the class [2]. Virtual experiments contribute to the creation of physical ideas and the formation of physical concepts; they specify, make more understandable and convincing the teacher's reasoning when presenting new material, arouse and maintain students' interest in the subject. With the help of a virtual experiment, the teacher guides the students' train of thought when studying phenomena and connections between them. From this follows an inviolable rule for a physics teacher: the virtual must be organically connected with his word, with the material presented - this is one of the most important conditions for the successful formation of physical concepts. Virtuals teach students to look for the source of knowledge in physics in the phenomena of the external world, in experience, which is invaluable for the formation of their dialectical-materialistic worldview. Virtual experiments are an organic part of the lesson. They can be the initial element for an explanation, illustrate and accompany a story, conversation, explanation and lecture by a teacher, and confirm what is stated. Virtual experiments are also used to set experimental tasks and when questioning students and repeating what they have learned. All this leads in school conditions to the need to conduct specially organized virtual experiments in the classroom that are necessary for teaching. In addition to the important role of virtual experiments in mastering the content of new educational material, they are of great importance in developing experimental skills in students.

4. Methods and techniques for conducting a virtual experiment

It is absolutely clear that the effect of any experiment primarily depends on the quality of school physics instruments. First of all, the following requirements are imposed on them: high technical qualities, simplicity of design, sufficiently large sizes, aesthetic design. The demo installation should be as simple as possible. This is important for understanding the experience and drawing conclusions from it. Installations should use devices that are known to students or whose operating principles are understandable to them. However, as the history of the development of physics teaching methods testifies, the simplicity and complexity of a particular virtual are relative concepts [3]. Thus, until recently, experiments showing the properties of electromagnetic waves, the polarization of light and the laws of the photoelectric effect were considered complex and almost never carried out in high school. With the advent of such instruments in the arsenal of physics classrooms as a set of instruments for studying the properties of electromagnetic waves, a school electronic oscilloscope, and a set of instruments for studying the polarization of light, these experiments became widespread.

5. Research results and discussions

One of the options for including a virtual experiment in a laboratory workshop is to use ready-made computer models to conduct a virtual experiment along with a real physical experiment [4]. Integrating two types of experiment can significantly expand the opportunities for observation, research and understanding of physical processes, and intensify students' activities in analyzing facts and putting forward hypotheses. At the same time, the effectiveness and feasibility of conducting a virtual experiment are largely determined by the compatibility of the interactive computer model and the real physical installation used in the laboratory workshop. However, despite the large number of already existing computer interactive models, the development of software tools that correspond to and complement the fleet of real laboratory installations remains a fairly pressing task. Often, physics teachers themselves decide to develop their own programs in order to solve the specific didactic problems they face [5]. This approach is very labor-intensive and requires not only a lot of time, but also good knowledge of information technology. Another

option for including a virtual experiment involves students conducting computational experiments using independently developed computer programs based on selected mathematical models of physical processes.

6. Materials and methods

6.1. Virtual experiments in the subject of physics

6.1.1. Diffraction pattern

A stylized three-dimensional image of the experimental setup includes a source of monochromatic radiation, an obstacle in the form of a screen with a system of parallel slits, and a screen for observing the diffraction pattern. The light beam coming from the source and the corresponding redistribution of the light flux that occurs after the obstacle are depicted in the color range of the visible radiation range in accordance with the selected wavelength. To the left of the installation, a 2B image of the diffraction pattern and an intensity distribution graph corresponding to this pattern are reproduced [6].

Figure 1. The main program window with a graphical user interface.

For user convenience, there is an interface with which you can change the main characteristics of the installation, as well as adjust animation settings (display an intensity graph, a measuring grid, a diffraction pattern, use an interactive ruler, scale images). The interface allows you to interactively control the process by changing several characteristic parameters: radiation wavelength, number of slits, slit width, distance between slits and distance from the obstacle to the observation screen. The “interactive ruler” tool, implemented using a mouse, allows you to measure the

characteristic distances between the maxima and minima of the diffraction pattern, similar to how this happens in a real physical experiment.

6.1.2. Fraunhofer diffraction

On the other hand, to demonstrate diffraction phenomena in the optical range, along with classical experiments, a compact installation has been developed and introduced into the educational process, allowing visual observation of the most famous diffraction experiments in a large lecture hall. The technical and methodological capabilities of the new virtual installation make it possible, without changing anything on the virtual table, to observe Fraunhofer diffraction from a narrow slit and on a diffraction grating; Fresnel diffraction from a round hole and (or) from an opaque disk.

Figure 2. Virtual installation for observing light diffraction

A photograph of the virtual installation is shown in Fig. 2. A semiconductor laser is used as a light source in the optical circuit, generating light at a wavelength of 532 nm (green region of the visible spectrum). The obstacle at which light is diffracted can be either an opaque disk on a glass substrate, or an opaque screen with a set of holes, or a standard optical slit, the width of which can be smoothly varied from 0.01 to 0.4 mm. An obstacle is placed between two lenses. The first lens (negative) forms a diverging laser beam, the second (positive, short-focus) builds an enlarged image of the diffraction pattern on the screen in the audience. The optical powers of the lenses, the sizes of obstacles and the distances between individual elements are selected in such a way that the transition from one diffraction pattern to another requires minimal changes in the optical design.

7. Comparative assessments of the quality of individual stages of laboratory work

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Table 1 - Survey about the virtual laboratory, %.

Questions	Yes, it is very effective, %.	Not, I have no idea, %	It is difficult to answer, %.
No.	1	2	3
Answers	28	62	10

An survey was conducted in School № 18 Jizzakh city, among primary schoolchildren regarding their knowledge of virtual laboratories and their feasibility of using them in the school curriculum. 50 schoolchildren's of grades 3a and 3b took part in the study. A theoretical review of the literature, conversations with children's, observations of them during physics classes and a questionnaire survey. Before the lesson, the children's were asked several questions.

To the question: “Is it effective to conduct a virtual laboratory?” the following responses were received (Table 1).

As we know that in education, digital literacy of teachers plays an important

Fig. 3. Survey about the virtual laboratory

role, who can freely use a personal computer, communicate with the community and students; in education they update their resources with the help of electronic technologies, which implement a system of tasks performed by students in electronic form. At the end of the course, we conducted a survey to test students' literacy in the field of information and communication technologies; the results of the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Indicators of the use of information and communication technologies by students at the end of the course.

Name of ICT	Usage indicators			
	Constantly, %	Often, %	Rarely, %	Habitually
Online classes	3	12	65	20
Virtual laboratory	0	60	40	0
Power Point program	45	45	8	2

The table shows that the use of electronic whiteboards, electronic textbooks, as well as the use of virtual laboratories when performing laboratory work created the opportunity to increase the competence of students in the field of information and communication technologies. From Table 2, we can see that students' use of online database and power point increased. The reason is that during the course, students used an electronic database for independent work and a Power Point program for preparing presentations. The results of the study show that according to the survey

conducted at the beginning of the course, we see that by the end of the course, students' use of information and communication skills increased by 10-15%.

Figure 4 - Schedule for improving students' information and communication skills.

Therefore, the use of electronic textbooks, electronic whiteboards and virtual laboratory programs during the lesson plays a key role in improving the information and communication skills of students. Modern information technologies speed up all stages of the educational process. Based on the use of information technology, we can observe an increase in the quality and efficiency of the educational process, and an increase in the cognitive activity of students.

Thus, virtual laboratories are organically integrated into the modern educational process, occupying their unique niche in the wide variety of didactic tools offered within the framework of the educational technologies used. Analysis of the implementation of virtual systems in our experience allows us to draw the following conclusions. The use of virtual laboratory work has made it possible to reduce the time allocated for them, as well as transfer some aspects of it into an independent mode of operation. The use of virtual laboratory work allows not only to strengthen the practical skills of students, but also to transfer part of the fund of assessment tools to virtual situational tasks. This allows not only to assess the student's practical skills, but also to track his readiness to pass the qualifying exam in the professional module.

Conclusion

Thus, we can conclude that the methods of teaching physics have always been more complex than the methods of teaching other subjects. The use of computers in teaching physics, the use of new information technologies, and their products deform the methodology of its teaching both in the direction of increasing the effectiveness of teaching and in the direction of facilitating the teacher's work. This will be another step towards improving the quality of education for schoolchildren and, ultimately, towards educating a new personality - responsible, knowledgeable, capable of solving new problems, quickly mastering and effectively using the knowledge necessary for this. Virtual experience can have pedagogical value only if the achieved effect of the virtual is clearly visible to the entire audience of students. Here one cannot but agree with the opinion of those who believe that no matter how perfect the virtual may be in all other respects, it will be unsuitable if the students do not so much see the phenomenon as guess about it from the words of the teacher.

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